

Supplementary Table 3: List of primers used.

Gene	Accession Number	Forward	Reverse
Sox2	NM_011443.3	CACAACCTCGGAGATCAGCAA	CTCCGGGAAGCGTGTACTTA
Oct3/4	NM_013633.2	CCAATCAGCTTGGGCTAGAG	CTGGGAAAGGTGTCCCTGTA
Nanog	NM_028016.2	TACCTCAGCCTCCAGCAGAT	GTGCTGAGCCCTTCTGAATC
PW1	NM_008817.2	TTTTGGTGAGTTGCTTGCAG	ACGTTCTTGGGCATAACTGG
CD34	NM_133654.3	GGGTAGCTCTCTGCCTGATG	TCTCTGAGATGGCTGGTGTG
SCA1	NM_001271446.1	CCATCAATTACCTGCCCCTA	AAGGTCTGCAGGAGGACTGA
CD45	NM_011210.3	CCTGCTCCTCAAACCTTCGAC	GACACCTCTGTCTGCCTTAGC
GAPDH	NM_008084.2	ACCCAGAAGACTGTGGATGG	CACATTGGGGGTAGGAACAC
β -actin	NM_007393.3	AGCCATGTACGTAGCCATCC	TCTCAGCTGTGGTGGTGAAG
α -sarc	NM_009606.2	AAGTGCGACATCGACATCAG	AAGTGCGACATCGACATCAG
MHC	NM_001039545.2	CCAAGCTGACCAAGGAGAAG	CCAAGCTGACCAAGGAGAAG
SMA	NM_007392.3	GCTGTCCCTCTATGCCTCTG	GAAGGAATAGCCACGCTCAG
Desmin	NM_010043.1	TACACCTGCGAGATTGATGC	ACATCCAAGGCCATCTTCAC
CD31	NM_001032378.1	GCCTCACCAAGAGAACGGAAGGC	TGGGCCTTCGGCATGGAACG
vWF	NM_011708.4	TGCCCTTGTGTGTGCACGGG	GTACCCTGGCTGCTGCACCG
CD146	NM_023061.2	GAGCTCATCTCCCCTCACAG	TCCTGACCACTACCCAAAGG
Ck18	NM_010664.2	CGAGGCACTCAAGGAAGAAC	CTTGGTGGTGACAACCTGTGG
Ck19	NM_008471.2	CTCGGATTGAGGAGCTGAAC	TCACGCTCTGGATCTGTGAC
Albumin	NM_009654.3	GACAAGGAAAGCTGCCTGAC	TTCTGCAAAGTCAGCATTGG
HNF1 α	NM_009327.3	ACTTGCAGCAGCACAAACAT	GAATTGCTGAGCCACCTCTC
β -3-tubulin	NM_023279.2	CATGGACAGTGTTCCGGTCTG	TGCAGGCAGTCACAATTCTC
ChAt	NM_009891.2	GTAACAGCCCAGGAGAGCAG	AGGTGTTGCATGCACTGAAG
ENO2	NM_013509.2	TCTATCGCCACATTGCTCAG	AGGGTGTGGTACACCTCTGC
GFAP	NM_001131020.1	CACGAACGAGTCCCTAGAGC	ATGGTGATGCGGTTTTCTTC